

Epistemological Extrapolation and Individually Targetable Mass Surveillance the Issues of Democratic Formation and Knowledge Production by Dictatorial Controls

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Abstract:- The paper summarizes the research the author conducted under the individually targetable mass surveillance systems of the P. R. China dictatorial regime with cyber sovereignty claims. In the complexities of cyber security and mass surveillance, the author adopted natural epistemology in counteracting dictatorial power influences for the resilience for democratic formation and for scientific research security from being utilized by autocratic power ambitions. The research generated some qualitative aspects of evidence and analysis on the dictatorial and autocratic power imposition via market incrementalism that impacts on international relations. The document also serves as a supplement to the author's astronomical researches. Even though the astronomical researches primarily served for the author's mental and psychological health, the a posteriori confirmation and analysis with empirical researches in white hole and black hole gradually becomes of the author's scientific priority. Both the astronomical and social science researches suggest, even with the growing emphasis on data in the STEM and social sciences, without proper values and scientific rigor, the growing popularity in big data may risk of a bubble economy in modern science.

Keywords:- human trafficking; mass surveillance; dictatorship; democratization; risk management.

I. INTRODUCTION

The worst enemy to democratic polity and democratization is the suppression on the fundamental freedoms such as freedom of expression and academic freedoms. Such suppressions are often aimed at eliminating elements of ideas and thinking from conceptualization that can have influence to social epistemology which is not in the interest of the predominant potentate. Albeit the fundamental differences in gender is on sexual attraction, the argument on methodological monism in natural epistemology denies on the inevitability of individualistic becoming, hence the inevitability of monist elements in the epistemologies of natural beings. [26] However, dictatorial regimes amplify such monism with autocratic governance and unitary party politics in seek of a collective monism with individually oppressive ideologies so that the socially recognizable predominant monist elements can effectively eradicate diversity in the governmental and societal systems. Such elements are often used for the advantage of power politics

that can effectively mobilize the society as the formation of nationalism. [2] In this regard, the author's natural epistemology as a self-identified homosexual male who grew up in a being criminalized legal-political environment shaped the analytical perspective in the paper.

People's Republic of China started to introduce heavy surveillance with public funding since the 2008 Beijing Olympics whereby a temporary practice on proclaimed antiterrorist measurement became a routine practice spread nationwide. Such proclaimed defense strategy on limiting the freedom of society did not justify itself when the author did an independent survey on proliferation issues in Beijing city in 2010 with the gamma ray indicators in cinematic arts with private interviews implying on the military production and testing sites, and possible underground production to the layers lower than the Beijing subway in later conversations in the society in Beijing. [8] During the private interviews, the author was also alerted on the deployed surveillance technologies in the telecommunication sectors in P. R. China for personal safety. The author hoped that for the population flow in Amsterdam where the exhibition was held, some relevant experts can notice the artwork with the adjacency to the Hague. The author came out to his peers and some professors in his undergraduate studies in Communication University of China, and with democratic procedures, the graduation coproduction was voted to be on transgender love and social identity. The peer discussions also led to a heterosexual girl's documentary on the marriage issues in P.R.China whereby under the injustice of law and sociopolitical pressures, LGBT persons got into heterosexual marriages. Albeit the author tried to put conceptualizations of homosexual love and marriage into cinematic practices, several times the investments got withdrawn due to the heavy censorships of the regime.

Historically, the cinematic sector was adopted by the Chinese Communist Party for propaganda purposes and ideology formation, and several prominent companies were used to launder arms trade currencies, such as the Bona Film Group Ltd. from the industrial knowledge the author acquired as an editor after graduation. Since every major company is required to have a CCP branch, the internal auditing and overseas military surrogacy companies became a cause for the offshore realm issues. [27] Furthermore, since the establishment of the China Banking and Insurance Regulatory Commission, the monetary flows became further

disguised systematically with several insurance companies directly tied to military production that negatively affect public health. Such models of economy substantially harm the macroeconomy and human rights under such an economic banking with financial coercions. American Embassy in Beijing reported on the P.M. 2.5 indicators for many years. No correlative data were gathered between the cancer rates in Beijing city and the military production pollutions, for such quantitative research is prone to be restricted by the regime government bodies. Since all flows of goods crossing the Chinese customs borders are bound for introspection, the systematic operations can only be a top-down design. The privatization of the once state capitalist China Mobile company with surveillance deployments further created the risks of privacy intrusion on a large scale.

The author edited an internal pitch video made for the Ministry of Public Security of PRC in 2015, and was further made aware of the cyber security issues the totalitarian order posed in relation to the Freedom of Information Act and privacy data, especially after Apple Inc. outsourced its servers to a company located in Guizhou province in mainland China, where the VISA processing center is also located and controlled by a company that may or may not be associated through the CCP channels. [7] (Further leads can be gotten from the author's private contact.) During the author's graduate studies at the MBA program in Communication University of China since 2015, he was fed with many information on the military movements during the rivalries between Xi Jinping and Bo Xilai. In order to gain power back to seat in the central government of the Chinese regime, Bo Xilai seized military control on the Chengdu military zone and controlled the Chongqing television for his propaganda base. Several times Bo Xilai sent the Chengdu military to the location of the central government Zhongnanhai. Unlike how the Chinese Embassy based on New York is guarded by New York Police Department (NYPD), embassies in mainland China are mostly guarded by the military, except for the American Consulate in Guangzhou.

The author shared some analysis in some classes and with some peers, which could have been utilized by some political forces. During the power rivalry, Wang Lijun got into the American Embassy in Chengdu reporting on Bogu Kailai's alleged murdering of a British businessman that was suspected to be an intelligence personnel. However, the whole process how Wang Lijun got into the American Embassy in Chengdu and bypassed the Chengdu Military Zone controlled by Bo Xilai, if the case were true and if Bo Xilai tried to cover up the alleged crime, has been deeply dubious. Later, both Bogu Kailai, and her husband Bo Xilai were both put into prison by Bogu Kailai's murder allegations created further questions on how equal protection failed the case. Even if Bogu Kailai's murder allegations were true and convicted, her husband's protection cannot be the basis of persecution, hence imprisonment. This led to the question on if the persecution was a political framing under the pretense of law. This question was corroborated by several personal contacts who may have lead to further government insider knowledge on the processes, even though the methods of propaganda Bo Xilai used in power

consolidation in the region was no different than how Xi Jinping uses on consolidation of power in the whole country. The only difference in the power control is the empowerment of data backends, including with privatized telecommunication surveillance. The anti-corruption political campaign initiated by the current dictatorial potentate was later institutionalized as National Supervisory Commission before the constitutional change of P. R. China.

The author's research started in 2017 before the constitutional change and consolidation of power in the Chinese higher education system, hence in UNESCO. The university where the author attended graduate studies were under nominal discourse on reform for years before the headmaster was removed by the anticorruption campaign for placing a student's gift in the headmaster's office and used the university car for private reasons for a few times, and was replaced by a possible alumnus from Xi Jinping's legal studies in Renmin University.

II. RESEARCH PROCESS

A. Initial Research

After a not legalized destructive homosexual partnership during the author's graduate studies, he went to the Beijing LGBT Center after noticing on the LGBT identity lecture delivered by professor Ilan H. Meyer in July 2017. The author noticed one of the two friends professor Meyer introduced and felt an instant connection on how he thought deeply by the side of the room. The author posed a very deep epistemological question and conundrums faced by the destructive partnership to John E. Pachankis and he answered well in a normative manner. Even though the author came out to his friends, parents, and some professors in school previously, he never came out as a Christian for his diligence on the Chinese political system's violence on people with religion. Nor did the author entail any political issues under analysis at that time. Later after a WeChat Group was founded based on the lecture, the author took the hint and attended Dr. Pachankis' presentation in Yale Center Beijing. Knowing deeply about the intelligence deployments in WeChat, the author added Dr. Pachankis' WeChat and deliberately invited him on a date and casual sex, after noticing he was reporting to the Beijing United Nations Office on LGBT matters and using WeChat. The author sensed the intimacy immediately shaped at that time, but needed to push him away for his protection. Without legal marriage, the author's intended's whole life and career may be under peril if utilized by the political forces in Beijing.

Apart from some indirect messages, the author noticed that John Pachankis' answers in the Q&A section was known to the dean of School of Economics and Management, which further created suspicions on the intelligence flows inside the regime. Furthermore, Beijing LGBT Center has always been listed as a cultural company and not an NGO, which means the unitary party dictatorial constitutional structure and party-interest orientated interpretative constitutional legislature is a threat to the fundamental-human-rights-orientated organization. The author adopted a social theater strategy to deal with the individually targetable mass surveillance human trafficking technologies thence. At that time, the author still

tried to make constructive changes in the intercultural realm, in consideration on the cultural epitomes of war incentives the dictatorial regime may exercise during the military power consolidation with the pretense of anticorruption campaign. Such systemic and structural issues were the deep troubles the author was facing. During the research process, the author wrote several pieces to his graduate academic supervisor Ouyang Changlin on the military issues and sent via WeChat for the potential dangers of a coup d'état imposed by the artificial intelligence empowered mass propaganda power control, and in relation to possible multiparty democratization with the "national reunification" discourses the regime asserts. However, the supervisor was removed from the university at that time also for his previous reforms in Hunan Television that severed the bureaucratic branches of the CCP to the television station that first symbolized the depropagandation of television production in mainland China. As of now, Ouyang Changlin seems to have made the compromise with the dictatorship and followed the ideological track in Communication University of China.

After a Foreign Direct Investment seminar held in Yale Center Beijing, the author got into contact with American Chamber of Commerce president William Zarit. After knowing he was accompanying former president Donald Trump for the first visit in Beijing, the author hinted him to be cautious on the hotel facilities, whereby the author was not sure if those technologies were used in the diplomatic occasions. In analyzing the Obama administration's policy deficiency in China in the economic realm, the author further researched on the underground academic businesses in P. R. China suggested by a graduate studies peer. The businesses seemed to have comprehensive economic data on America that is not available in any public nor private sources behind the paywall. Furthermore, when the author asked about drawing Foreign Direct Investment, it systemically triggered the FDI laws P. R. China enacted to impose on monetary supremacy in the international realm. This meant that such companies could have been a link to the military backends in the double-entry bookkeeping system of the centralized Chinese banking system with economic intelligence inside the American economic system.

The author visited the U.S. in 2018 for the first time upon Brexit and the Trade War to investigate on the actual economic indicators in everyday life. The purchasing power parity was far more reasonable than P. R. China, and justified the Trade War based on the military expansionism of P. R. China. The author heard from a private source that the Guangzhou military zone was prepared to attack Taiwan on the same day before the news on the constitution change that made P. R. China from a coup d'état to de facto dictatorship and consolidated by the power political consolidation with nominal "law". The author was asked if he wanted a Green Card on the acting class where he saw the news, he said no for the reason on the potential humanitarian crisis of war and wanted to do what he can to prevent that. After making sure on the safekeeping practices possibly with the intervention from Johns Hopkins University's based in Nanjing, the author made further researches on the histories of war in global politics and shifted to online courses by the background information on America's deployment of the

platforms.

B. Further Research and Locating the Problem

For the purpose of the primary focus on nonproliferation, arms control, and disarmament, the author did further research on the nuclear knowledge flow in the international realm amidst the war histories, especially in relation to the peaceful development in outer space. [17] Evidences suggested that the use of thermonuclear weapon by America in World War II was to protect the NASA Deep Space Network, yet the dictatorial consolidation of power politics was the main purpose for Russia and P. R. China with power politics projections. [4] [25] These researches were initiated by P. R. China's Xinhua News propagandas in opposing America's use of nuclear technologies in outer space, which the author intuitively thought to be a plausible practice. [16]

During the researches, the author noticed that P. R. China started to set up new majors in intelligence in the publication industry in the military affiliated universities, and found the key evidence on the reason of such deployment. [30] Ontological computation on academic publications is prone to endanger the healthiness of the global academic and scientific practices and with mass media production, let alone the privacy data the regime may have always had. Further researches suggested that psychological data collected may also be prone to be codified by Chinese cyber practices. With such information and understanding, the author went to the U.S. in 2019 in seek of asylum to report to the American government on the potential danger it poses in relation to the dictatorial practices such a power has on the security council with massive humanitarian abuses. The author changed his SIM card at the JFK airport in New York in 2019 upon arrival, and bought a new MacBook Pro in New Haven. However, the asylum filing failed and the author had to return to the regime after the attendance on the *International Cooperation in the National Interest: In Defense of the Multilateral System* seminar held in Yale University.

It is both for the author's psychological health and ridicules for the mass surveillance privacy intrusion in a homophobic regime, the author adopted artistic practices in homosexual sex that does not violate human morality and in the meantime put on sexual contents inside the surveillance network as a humanitarian protest and load on the privacy intrusion systems. It is also an ethical defiance on how heterosexual marriages are justified by having children in the societal normalcy yet LGBTQIA marriage equality is questioned on the basis of "sex quality", especially that the regime has always imposed birth control and measurements on the society for its short-term power needs disregarding the fundamental freedoms and dignities of humanity for its power enslavement. It is also for this reason, equal marriage in the context of the regime environment is not in the issue of gender diversity, but the lack of justice in the concept and spirit of law itself. A professor from the author's undergraduate studies hinted on the issue by suggesting on *The Spirit of the Laws* by Montesquieu.

C. Victimization by Human Trafficking

After return, the author was targeted on gay social media several times during the final version of dissertation writing. The trafficker’s blinking locations may have come from Guangzhou near the American Embassy and the author judged it to be from the Chinese military intelligence. The trafficking started when the author’s mother asked for a loan from her sister to support the author’s living expenses and sent to him via WeChat. To identify the intension on the targeting, the author got into contact with the human trafficker by request on WeChat. It was when the author admitted that he fell in love with an American the human trafficker(s) got into psychological attacks apart from the financial attacks. One of the companies the human trafficker(s) used for bridging monetary flows was affiliated with China Academy of Sciences, records of which on AliPay was deleted from the backend when the author tried to retrieve the data as evidence.

The author kept a recording with an old iPhone 4 for evidence, and traced the human trafficker(s)’ identities as shown in Figure 2. When the author went to the police the following day, the police only asked for snapshots of the evidences. The author provided to the police, and asked that if he needed the recording. The police said no. The police asked the author to call the human trafficker, and talked code-like on the police department’s location with the sign on oil station. The police asked the author to beg so that the human trafficker can send the money back to the author. The author refused to adopt such unjust and demeaning compromise for the coercion. Several days later, the author was contacted via cellphone call with someone claiming to be the police asking for the recording that is needed for evidence. The author knew he only told the police on it and told the person where the author was living in. Several days later, the iPhone 4 kept in a drawer with the recording was missing, with the laptop on the desk intact. And the author received a snapshot from the body-worn video with police timestamp, with the message warning the author cannot keep the evidence. The author knew for sure then the police is a part of the organized crime done by the government. It was also at that instant, the author’s psychological defense collapse again. From the recollections on the blinking signals and possible right location of the human trafficker, it can be from the same sources of attack from the Titan Rain associated with the People’s Liberation Army. The research process corroborated with the judgement that the graduate course designs were mandated by the military-intelligence complex that is against the proper values the author has always held. The human trafficking attack reaffirmed the author’s intuitive decisions to protect his intended with dichotomic expressions.

Fig.1: Police return from the incident which cannot be queried in the government system.

Fig. 2: Evidence of One of the Human Trafficker's Bank Account

Since the author was not able to get inside the university which was under military lockdown with armed forces department inside the university, the author formed the final version of his dissertation after a brief rehabilitation from the temporary traumas and sent to the university library email before returning to his parents' in Chongqing. [5] The author's judgements on the whole process were corroborated by his high school mathematics teacher and then classmate working in the National University of Defense Technology, with a grief-like greeting saying that the author has rich kindreds. Not soon afterwards, the news came out that the doctor Wenliang Li (李文亮) was brought to the police station for punitive measures for letting the public know about the SARS-structured virus and the potential dangers to public health. Knowing the totalitarian and autocratic cyber intelligence on Chinese social media, and personal trust on the aforementioned individuals even within and under the dictatorial institutions, the author cursed the CCP on WeChat friendzone, indicating to the virus and appealed to the memories on the disasters created by SARS. The military associated medical schools in Chongqing first responded and sent first aid to Wuhan with military jets. However, in the meantime, the Chinese government obstructed the World Health Organization listing it as global health emergency by influencing the Chinese and African delegates with concerns for trade and monetary reasons the liberal institution may trigger in the global economy. The news piece was written with a nationalism tone. And the records on WeChat friendzone were deleted from the backend after the freezing of the author's account. It was after the COVID-19 pandemic when the author tried to focus on the one thing that makes him happy for mental health reasons, he got some positive scientific results. [6] Yet the research, especially the white hole observation data analysis on the Trifid Nebula, further triggered the memories on the fundamental basis of the author's theory on nuclear physic-chemistry applied to the fundamental forces in cosmology, and impacted on the author's mental health again with the close observation and discovery on the nuclear binding force between the black hole and white hole that may constitute as the fifth fundamental force. [22] It was for the author being pushed to pursue his undergraduate degree in the Chinese military affiliated universities or Tsinghua University in high school with the background knowledge on the past nuclear wars and human rights abuses of the Chinese regime the author chose to study and work in the humanities. Under the ongoing military dictatorship and coercions, the author thought to keep such a knowledge hidden and take it to his grave was the best choice. Fortunately, the *Teaching Astronomy* team, the *Astropedia* community, and possibly professor Chris David Impey may have noticed that. With the encouragement on knowledge production, and the grief that the author did not have the chance to meet Steven Weinberg before his passing-away, the author is gradually recovering from the trauma.

Fig. 3: The WeChat Account Blocking by the Chinese Cyber Intelligence

III. METHODOLOGY

With the Chinese cyber environment, whereby no privacy exists in society or in personal communications, and with the knowledge on the machine learning deployments whereby propaganda generation are further powered by artificial intelligence, ontological data mining, and even psychological data coding, the social theater approach that can be seen as contrary to the “social norms” for the human traffickers, people behind the mass surveillance, and mass psychological reinforcement purposed to achieve with such technologies, were used to generate evidences in the systemic construct, imposing phenomena that addresses on the humanities' conceptualizations against the machines algorithms. [30] A homosexual male body art photography was created at that time on the intricate aspects between gender and sociopolitical constructs. Besides, such methods of evidence gathering does not need to intrude the systems while preserving the humanities needed in such an unhuman construct. And by speaking out the truths behind the analyses that many people fear to voice, the key triggers on the censorship mechanisms also corroborates with the key information strands on the truths the systemic deployments seek to suppress and bury, as shown in *Figure 8*.

With the ontological constructs in Chinese cyber from the mass epistemological extrapolations, the epistemological monism the author holds became consistent reference points against the systemic mass media approaches and the Chinese cyber impositions. [3] These cognitive resources were gained from the author's professional experiences as an editor in the

industry and enhanced by the conscious management of the self's consciousness. [13] Apart from the epistemological monism in social sciences, the invariant Hawking points in relation to the author's white hole research were also enhanced by consistent interactions with the astronomical communities in scientific exchanges and positive social interactions. [22] For the author's previous notices in the research activities that many technological companies based in P. R. China gathers voice print, facial cognition, and keyboard text input monitoring for social calculations, the author adopted linguistic changes in expressions to counteract the systemic calculations as was done with his dissertation writing, whereby he condensed the solar notion of time into several sentences in simplified Chinese. [5] During the cyber security research, the author installed Federal Common policy authority certificate on the iPhone and enabled input monitoring by NASA's Eyes APP to counteract the technical effects posed by the cyber sovereignty claims of P. R. China. Such trust is based on the author's prerequisite researches on the American military and organizational motivations that is better justified than the Chinese militaries. The prerequisites behind the astronomical research served as risk management apart from the mentally constructed security protocols in instrumentation safety denoted by vector Hamiltonian zero. [22]

Fig. 5: NASA's Eyes' Informed Consent on Input Monitoring

During the rehabilitation of the author's social functioning after the harms and trauma from the human trafficking, Christianity played a critical role. However, sexually explicit informatics from unidentified sources in gay social media targeting were also detected during the process. Since the communications lines inside the regime are heavily guarded, it is plausible that many American officers' privacy data were breached and harnessed during their commissions in mainland China by the Chinese military, without exclusion on probabilities in sexual captivity that is not an uncommon phenomenon in the Chinese military school. The spiritual connections the author has with John Pachankis have been the key component keeping the author's faiths in justice and marriage both for the self and the LGBTQI community at large, even though during the process, for many pragmatic reasons, he may have entered a civil union with someone he has always known. On a defiance action on the justice of law, the author certified a notarial act in mainland China that he was never married. It was both by the fact of territorially based power paradigm of law and interpretations of law that serves as the power extension, and for the evidence that the laws in China is not legitimate. The author found the church online and attended prayers and atonements with the Universal Life Church based in Modesto, California. During the astronomical researches, the author was also contacted by some other unidentified sources that showed hints on knowing the author's data experiment in the cyber realm. [18] For the spiritual commitment the author has kept since 2003, he got ordained by the church in 2021. Seeing it was a legal ordination, with the spiritual relationship the author has with John Pachankis since 2017 and a representative in mind in the 2019 visit in New Haven, the author changed his last name to his in the ordination as for a marital act, with the middle name conceived on the self-revelation during the astronomical experiment and researches. Akin to the gender perceptions outlined in the United Nations charter framework, the imbalance of gendered hierarchy in the theological approaches in the global system is not without a

Fig. 4: The Federal Common Policy Authority Certificate Installed

cause to the LGBTQI situations worldwide. [23] [19] [21] Even with the legalization and legislative practices in the global north, many societal conceptualizations on marriage laws still consider it to be a sexual right granted to the LGBTQI persons as to the heterosexual perception of male might in the power(ed) hierarchy. However, the spirit outlined by the Rome Statute still serves as a public good in spite of the territoriality and extraterritoriality deficiencies the CCP tries to counteract with decolonialization discourses that harbor criminals and obstruct due justices in mass human rights abuses.

ordination document for identification. The author changed the appointment using the Chinese government issued identifications, but the Chinese and Chinese originated staff refused for further processing since the pending USCIS action cannot be queried by the system in the Embassy. (The author requested for a change of VISA status during the astronomical research as a precaution for the research being utilized by the Chinese military and military surveillance. Also when the author noticed the cold fusion on the NASA data, in writing on the research findings in the IAEA meeting with ITER complexities, the author submitted forms both on the Chinese and American governmental agents so that the information on the outer space environment can be addressed with minimal risks in international security.) Later, the author changed to the Chinese passport issuance department in Beijing with request for annotating his new name on the passport. One of the service persons who seems to be a lesbian asked about the name change with the ordination, and the author confided in her on the marital relationship. They assisted the author along the process. After returning to Chongqing in one phone call, another technical service person said that there was a national ban imposed on the author in the system. They took extra time to process the author's document and finally bypassed the Ministry of Public Security's system in the Chinese categorization of passports, with an immigration passport issued to the author.

Fig. 6: The Legal Document Confirming the Author's Ordination Currently Kept by a German Friend with the Church Bible

With the analytical framework, whereby Beijing LGBT Center is listed as NGO yet defined by the Chinese power as a cultural company, the lack in incentives of the unitary party politics governmental system in mainland China is the key reason for the human dignities of LGBTQI persons in the regime. This is also where the humanitarian clauses in the United Nations charter are often put in the argument as human rights. [9] However, such human rights arguments largely trapped itself under power politics, and neglected the fact that all persons are born equal and ought to be treated so. The low politics threatens P. R. China poses ought not to disturb the consistency of high politics that liberal institutionalism was purposed to serve, and it is also for this reason, the reforms of the United Nations system is critical as to the national politics that is undergoing in the Asian region. With the geopolitical expansionism and military ambitions disguised by cultural hegemony as "soft power", the top-down schemes putting LGBTQIA+ as subcultural population affiliated with the "mainstream culture" is a typical response by the sinocentric throwback approach in delusional cultural hegemony building that is consistent with using the cinematic arts companies for military import and money laundering. [28] In the process of fulfilling the legal processes as procedural justice, when the author was acquiring the travel documents, it was found that the author's ID card was associated with a telephone number that is unreachable in the Chinese immigration system. When the author attempted to get an American passport first in the American Embassy in Beijing, the author was blocked from entering with his

Fig. 7: The Telephone Number that was Linked to the Author's ID Card

To supplement on the existing evidences on the individually targetable human trafficking schemes, and along with some support to the university the author attended under the dictatorial coercion, the author adopted the social theater approach in the alumni WeChat groups. Even though the university is known to be a party propaganda generation platform, it is also known for its functions in the Chinese constitutional structures to limit the power expansions. The freedom of press was often taught in school despite of the media policies that are often imposed to constrain the proper functions the university stood for. Before the constitution change in mainland China, the departments with independent news spirit in the China Central Television were removed, and many influential persons were invited back to the university for teaching positions prior to the removal of the headmaster by anticorruption campaigns. By feeding the information to the alumni groups the author also intended to protect the dignities of the professionals from systemic violence with the dismantling of proper truths. The blocking

of the author’s WeChat account corroborated with the author’s analysis and generated the evidence on the system’s surveillance capacities. This also served as an informant to the professional community on how local and state governments use technologies to frame criminal sentences to journalists. However, with the ontological analytical tool and epistemology extrapolation in the Chinese affiliated cyber realm, the use of independent journalism ontology in making political campaigns may also had been utilized to redirect the public’s awareness to the power ideology.

IV. EPISTEMOLOGICAL REHABILITATION AND KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION IN THE AGE OF CYBER COMPLEXITY

It is for the research and research processes, the knowledge production process on the author’s astronomical research served as an epistemological rehabilitation process on the cosmological theory the author formed in high school that guided the research activities. In this regard, the worldview that may have rendered to the sub and unconsciousness of the author became explicit again in the process of knowledge production based on the empirical research activities. The traumatic responses on the complexities in the cyber realm accompanied the author’s writing processes, along with the psychological mechanism that rendered the early formed cosmological understanding to deeper levels of unconsciousness for the concerns on maluses of such knowledges that once contributed to the scourges of war and suffering. For the scientific conference the author is attending, the recording and speaking practices also helped in the rehabilitation on language and social functioning processes. In the globalized shape of the society and LGBTQI population, the emancipation and ethics is tricky both in personal relationships and knowledge production. In this regard, the writing and peer-review processes was also an exploration in the ethics between heterosexual normative perceptions and LGBTQIA+ scientists. [10]

By the quality of human law and democratic formation, the Republic of China founded by the retreated Kuomintang which desisted the CCP power groomed by Russian hegemony during the World War II and Cold War but marginalized in the United Nations security council with the nuclear weapon line across the strait is still the promising political entity in the Asian sphere and on maritime. Mainland China’s statutory and declarative rhetoric and discourses never held to its practices for the dictatorial and autocratic system and organizational behaviors. Such rhetoric and discourses may be further enhanced by the ontological data harnessing so that its diplomatic responses will always seem favorable to other political entities in the international and global realm. However, the substantial realities may never be so. [28] With the chaos in the Interpol for the previous years around P. R. China, the justice systems are under tremendous scrutiny with autocratic power politics players. Such political culture led on by P. R. China has also been reflected in American politics, which made the power mirroring on American democracy partially Chinese-like. In a paper the author submitted to an America incorporated publishing house that is confirmed to be operated by Chinese companies, whereby the author outlined the democratization path with constructive approaches on arms control, disarmament, and nonproliferation to a structure that does not contribute to the increase in conflicts, the contents were editorially suppressed from being published and the deputy editor hinted that the constant revision advices were only rhetoric. [20] By the spirit of the high politics with the empirical confirmation on the reasons the author focused on the humanities instead of astronomy previously, the conclusions in this paper remain unchanged, only that in order to achieve such an ideal, the technologies used as power political control on the civil society with centralized

Fig. 8: Evidence on WeChat’s Surveillance Capacity, Human Trafficking, and Privacy Violation

crypto-banking need to be restored to appropriate uses in the spirit of the fundamental freedoms of human beings.

It is also in this regard, in times of knowledge production by the suppression on proper conceptualizations and epistemological extrapolations in the global cyber realm with telecommunication surveillance and informatics, the realistic power dimension as in terms of the mass destructive measures, the positive and negative reinforcements in the market of idea place is substantially undermined and pooled with the CCP ideological interests in the incremental market. [1] The financial and economic coupling with power interdependence theory is only a façade on the global ideological expansionism that needs to be carefully examined, since the liberal institutions are also eroded with such top-down knowledge production designs. The sanction mechanisms in the liberal institutions used psychologically for negative and positive reinforcements are deeply shaping the future of human behaviors, organizational behaviors, intellectual development, collective unconsciousness in the sustainability and advancement of scientific advancements, and hence social fictions consisted of human beings. If and when a normative order based on dictatorial rule disguised in the liberal global system is established and proper values in knowledge prone to be epistemologically controlled, the cyber empire based on regional order manipulating the global realm will foul what we thought we knew.

In the gendered domain of law and politics, the United Nations system is inherently deficient for human rights abuses conducted by countries in the Permanent Five members, since the International Criminal Court (ICC) can only process cases referred to by the security council, or prosecute cases only when states do not or are unwilling or unable to do so genuinely. If no case is referred to the ICC from inside the CCP, the fact on the dictatorship in P. R. China is concluded to be a making of the party by its power political projections in the United Nations Security Council. This means that the crimes against humanity, whereby the militant dictatorship suppressed the free flow of vital information in the regional and global society with COVID-19, and obstructed the World Health Organization from listing it as global health emergency that rendered the first responses systemically obsolete, is not being investigated but should be persecuted even when P. R. China has been deleting vital information around the issues in the cyber realm. And only several local government personnel in the Wuhan government were dismissed as scapegoat under dictatorial rule. The retrospective consequence then is, it may have misled the British prime minister for introducing biased policy, and lowered the awareness in the global society by making the liberal institutions' organizational functions in the mitigation of common threats obsolete, and arbitrarily enacted marshal law only after bottom-up responses emerged, whereby such responses had no consideration for the distribution of vital resources in the global society with public health and epidemiology experts' instruction and coordination. (Several Chinese companies in America bought masks to assist Wuhan via international flight when the first bottom-up response started.) Such crime is consistent with the human trafficking monetary laundering with centralized banking and industrial bases for the militant expansionism

with power political games inside the security council, just as how the 1989 Tian'anmen Square Massacre remains unpunished, the killings and mass propaganda campaigns against the Falun Gong members remain unpunished which the author saw that survivors were harbored by the American government in New York. If the United Nations system failed to put justice into light again, it means that the liberal institutions are starting to lose legitimacy on the proper values and ideals it founded upon, with the structural loopholes constantly eroded by low power politics.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Brexit and the Trade War initially constrained the geopolitical expansionism P. R. China has been seeking through centralized banking with new technologies, including artificial intelligence and cryptocurrency. However, the Chinese cyber operations with illegitimate practices in arbitrary enactment of statutory law transferred the loss from military production and absolute power interest to the civil economy. The means the measures Trump administration adopted did not serve well on high politics, but was only a responsive act on the threat that started to surface. This was also the reason the author wrote on decoupling the Chinese RMB with USD in a Coursera class to mitigate the humanitarian risks such political actions can incur, even with the increase in military spending by P. R. China. However, possible evidences for further investigations could have been lost by a fire in American Embassy in Beijing during the trade war period, but the retrieval of the Embassy in Chengdu may have preserved some evidences at least for the complexities on Bo Xilai's case, hence probable evidences in the chain of events that led to the dictatorship by design or not. On the low politics aspect, the structural realist formation of geopolitical ambitions in the communist block results from the maladaptation of USSR on outer space development during the Cold War with the CCP as the devote follower. [25] The Belt Road initiative and the strategic banking with Russia in the South China Sea is only another geocentric energy politics game to vie for maritime power dominance, which could have been the low political reason for Brexit. The Federal Reserve system's recent responses in issuing cryptocurrency can be seen as a defensive response for the monetary manipulations that is still ongoing. [24]

Even with the concerns in low politics, the reunification discourses posed by the CCP is not a negative factor for democracy building for a stabilized Chinese sovereign with constitutional separation of powers, which underlies the KMT's historic approaches but failed during the Mao Zedong dictatorship with the Korean wars defending the Russian hegemony. [25] However, such discourse cannot be adopted to cater to the power ambitions and expansionism of the CCP. If with a national reunification agenda, multiparty democracy is the bottom-line. By the multiparty democracy, Republic of China has functionally adapted with high spirits in human law in the Asian political sphere, the democratization of mainland China with ROC's deep cultural-political knowledges and experiences is the key contributive factor for regional stability. However, with the telecommunication infrastructure P. R. China strategized to

marginally seize Taiwan and applied to coerce the civil society with mass surveillance and ontological data extrapolations, such cyber security and intelligence issues are difficult to resolve. This is also the reason why the dictatorship formation can be contributed by the privatization of the China Mobile Company, and the anti-corruption campaigns are only political persecution schemes. Otherwise, the privatization of the state capitalist company is the first corruption that needs to be dealt with rather than headmasters of universities that groom professional which have constitutional balance of power to the government, and can serve the ICC as informal expert.

Regardless of the practical conundrums, the first step to achieve the separation of power on the Chinese sovereign is through nuclear disarmament across the Taiwan Strait. [14] [15] The purpose for nuclear disarmament and constitutional separation of power can better foster military cooperation in the security council on NEO threat mitigation strategies that can both shape the advances in the peaceful development in outer space and the viable sustainability of civil economy. This can substantially decrease the marginal geopolitical conflicts the security council has contributed to, and make the ICC free from the burden on visible wars to the real humanitarian interests of high politics, such as the inactions and obstructions on global cooperation in times of eminent threats to the well-being of humanity. Such crimes against humanity is far more serious and diabolical than the multilateral and marginal conflicts. The predominant epistemological paradigm PRC has been adopting has been an outdated geopolitics and energy strategy in hiding arms production facilities underground to prevent it from air-raided shells and being detected by air-based and satellite-based detections, which is also reflected in the economic realm by conduction mechanism of monetary policy (货币政策传导机制). Such epistemological paradigm further blocked the civilization from anywhere near to form a proper military that is competent to manage earthly affairs. The advantages of Taiwan's planetary sciences in the Asian cultural sphere can further integrate with the established mainland organizations for military integration in order to form a coalesced independent military branch of power. The independence of military from the political branch is key to the reform on a clean-cut and clear-cut separation of power, which means the CCP needs to give up its claim on constitutional power and such power on the military. The strategic importance of the Asia-Pacific cannot be fully eradicated for fragmentation without allyship. The rising PLA maritime capabilities, if they proactively disarm, can mitigate the energy dilemma their military ambitions have put themselves into. [29] Furthermore, changes of the military organizations can contribute to less fragmented maritime security by cooperating with NATO as a strategic point linking the seas between the global North and South.

For the experience ROC has with humanitarian legislation and judicial experiences with better understanding on Chinese culture than using it for diplomatic rhetoric, the legal reform and Senate function ought to reside with the Taiwanese experts. A transitional electoral organization is needed for the change to a multi-party democracy instead of

the current "multi-party consultancy" dictated by the CCP power politics. This paradigm fits best into the human security theory and utility production instead of destructive production as proposed by Mary Kaldor on a global formation of global strategy. (Kaldor, 2011) The humanitarian and spirits of natural law the Taiwan judiciary systems with accumulated cases can further push for the legal reform mainland with a statutory law system needs that reflects a power political and patriarchal pattern of "legislation". [9] For this, the economic bubbles the Chinese military and CCP has created with communism would have to cool down after the global propagandist cultural expansionism, which has to come to an end. However, for the territorial technicality CCP uses against the ICC, the secondary clause on the principle of complementarity ought to be exercised as the balance of power concerning the crimes done by the P5 members, regardless of its nonmember and no signatory status. [12] Even though independent journalism in the sovereign is also coerced by the time being, research and information distributed in the international realm can still be relevant, and further reforms for independent journalism is still promising with the ICC for a healthy industry.

When the author attempted to share the ICC's function for independent journalism in the alumni group, the group is blocked for "violating the laws and regulations" as shown in *Figure 9*. This further proves that the power politics inside the regime has been further tightened and constitutes as "unable or unwilling to do so genuinely". It is worth noting that, even for the politics inside the CCP, the term limit set by Deng Xiaoping for concerns on dictatorship after the 1989 Tiananmen Square Massacre being abolished is also inconsistent with the party doctrine itself they claim to believe in. If no Chinese journalists have filed anything to the ICC based on current situations in mainland China or on the previous occasions that shaped the dictatorship, this further proves the reason why the headmaster of Communication University of China needed to be removed before the consolidation of the dictatorial power. It is also for such a top-down dictatorial act that also contributed to the pandemic disaster constituting as crime against humanity, Xi Jinping (习近平), the general secretary of the CCP, as the dictator with both the military power and presidential power, ought to be put into justice, apart from the actions similar to the case of Adolf Eichmann with ethnic nationalism ideologies that put the whole population of the regime on territorial imprisonment disregarding fundamental freedoms and human rights. [7] Such technologies, if used in purposes for power political gains on dictatorship formation, possible complice could have been in the high official and intelligence departments, including military intelligence. It is also by the empowerment of modern technologies and party institutionalism, assassinations combined with bureaucratic coercions are made possible to rival against the liberal foundations the United Nations is built upon. Such hidden dimensions of disfunction on liberal and neoliberal institutionalism is the main cause on marginal conflicts such as the recurring Ukraine crisis.

Fig. 9: The Group is Found Being Restricted on April 4 2022 by Rhetoric of “Laws and Regulations”

For the religiously based marriage in the context of separation of church and state, with the Chinese government denying on the annotation on the change of name, proceedings on the marital case needs to be heard by the American court. And for the coercion and human trafficking, such a mass violation on human rights and abuses to human rights need to be referred to the ICC. Even though the conclusions in the paper hold true on democratization of the Chinese sovereign, pragmatic situation suggests it is less likely to be actualized without first eradicating on the dictatorship which has offensive intensions in disregard on the welfare of humanity. Hence the “community for a shared future for mankind” should not be understood as a value centered on global cooperation, but a discourse for regional dominance on the Chinese cultural strategic thinking on “befriend the countries in further geological distances and seize smaller neighboring countries (远交近攻)”. Such conceptual differences ought not to be confused with “love thy neighbor” that underlies the regionalism for economic freedom conceptualized by the double movement. [11] For the intergovernmental discrepancies in name and transitional justice, the paper is authored in the “maiden name”.

VI. APPENDIX

Transliteration of figure contents:

A. Figure 1:

Acceptance Receipt

Beijing Police Chaoyang District (Pingfang) Acceptance Receipt Word [2019] No. 000851

Cao, Yang:

You (Unit) reported and claimed the case of Yang Cao being victimized by fraudulent operations on Year 2019 Month 09 Day 16 I unit have received (case accepted registration word number as Beijing Police Chaoyang District (Pingfang) Acceptance Receipt Word [2019] No. 000851).

You (Unit) can inquire on the case development via telephone to the unit received the case, or login to Beijing City Police Department “Case Registered Public Inquiry System” <https://gaj.beijing.gov.cn/lagk/login.do> (scanning the barcode below can login conveniently).

User account: Your national identity card or the identification document number provided when reported the case

Pin: 58609232

Contact and contact method: Cui, Shuo 85574138

(Barcode)

Beijing City Public Security Chaoyang Department

Case reporter, accuser, whistleblower, warrant

Pingfang Police Station

(seal)

2019 September 16

This copy is submitted to

Case reporter, accuser, whistleblower, warrant

B. Figure 2:

Transfer

Recipient: Wang, Xu 6228480218906518970

Transfer Amount

Payment Card: China Merchant Bank (3601)

Message notification:

Anticipated Payment Time according to Transfer Information

Next

• Instructions:

- For the safety of your money, do not trust the non-formal channel transfer requests in the name of public security, prosecutor, legal enforcement, leader or close relative and friends, surrogate for high amount of credit card and loans, fraudulent transaction, internet sales rep. or delivery refund, exacerbated large high return investment, to prevent fraud. Involving unknown monetary transfer, please must verify in person or over the telephone.
- Do not scan dubious barcode, do not install unverified APP, keep card number, passcode, SMS verification, and other important personal information intact.

C. *Figure 7:*
(Passport Issuance Portal)

Basic Information

ID Type: National ID

Name: Cao, *

ID Number: 50010319*****

Telephone Number: 17034094959

Sex: (tick) Male () Female

Address:

D. *Figure 8:*

Chat history: 282 persons in the group

Anonymized Person: ?

Author: Previously for many years the university was without a headmaster.

When Xi Jinping took power a possible alumnus of his from Renmin University was put on the post.

Around the time of constitution change.

The ministerial university reform was without a minister for many years, including the college deans.

I am not sure of the vice headmaster designated from the treasury department (in the political unrest).

The old headmaster is in Nanjing. Friends who are in the Southern part of China familiar with the institute histories of the university at least have some memory palace to go to.

But the spirit of independent report has never ceased with coup d'état.

Anonymized Person: (screenshot)

Author: Don't use power banks with (certain products). I tested it, it generates Jason files in the Apple system and can be associated with the intelligence processes.

I did an internal pitch editing for the Ministry of Public Security previously (on technologies that hacks smartphones and copy data files and implemented in some of such products or deployed in the hotels).

Now the university is under domain politics.

Maybe there is no equivalent wording for coup d'état in Chinese, but this is the fact and reality.

All these years the internal issues in the university I believe many of you should know something.

From unitary one-party rule to one man rule, this is a grave problem!

The suicides of the CFO of (Poly) Bona Films and a CEO on the Ministry of Railways of PRC are dubious.

This can be relevant to the free trade zones in Hainan province and supply chains to the South China Sea.

This is also related to the interests of the Shanghai branches of the CCP (after the fact on the former vice chairman of the Central Military Commission of China Caihou Xu's (徐才厚) arrest who served as a key person in the military after Zemin Jiang's (江泽民) retirement from chairmanship and balanced the nominal separation of power in Jintao Hu's (胡锦涛) presidency.)

Anonymized Person: Is your account stolen by someone?

Author: No.

Anonymized Person: (emoji)

Anonymized Person: Please bro, if you have any speech they can be communicated privately, the group is a peer support group, no need to put personal stances in here. If the group is blocked, there is no good for any of us~

Anonymized Person: Respect your stand, opinion, but please be aware of occasion~

Author: Read more books. This is fact not opinion.

If the group is blocked and not my personal account, what would this mean?

Anonymized Person: don't know

Anonymized Person: Tips tips

Anonymized Person: LOL

(The author's account got individually blocked soon afterwards.)

E. *Figure 9:*

Chat history: CUC Directing Major Group (280)

Author: BTW, the test result is, WeChat can directly see the chat contents via backend and block account individually. I am reorganizing an article, and found an ICC document, sharing here. Worthwhile the reading and learning. Especially who now works in journalism.

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1 Corinthians 10: 3-5 (GOD'S WORD Translation).

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